

Influence of anodization parameters of first step on structural features of porous anodic alumina (PAA) finally formed in phosphoric acid

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Abstract : Porous anodic alumina (PAA) is a versatile template for the fabrication of nanomaterials. To obtain highly ordered nanopore array, two step anodization process is a much less expensive method than other methods like lithography, optical diffraction grating etc. The PAA template was fabricated by two step anodization process. The first step proceeded in oxalic acid to different extent of anodization time and at different voltages to predict the influence of anodization conditions in the first step on the morphology and microstructure of porous anodic alumina film formed in phosphoric acid in the second step. The time varied from 10 to 120 min and voltage varied from 20 to 50 V in the first step anodization. Second step of anodization was constant for all experiments and proceeded in 0.3 M H₃PO₄ for 120 min at 70 V. The morphology of the PAA was studied by field emission scanning electron microscope (FE-SEM). The reflectance spectrum was recorded and thickness of oxide films was determined from the reflectance data. The results show that longer is the anodization time in the first step in oxalic acid, higher is the symmetry of pores as well as higher is the pore density in finally formed PAA in phosphoric acid. The best voltage for pre-texturing in first step was found to be 40 V. It resolved that first step anodization in oxalic acid reduced the applied voltage required to obtain the symmetrical hexagonal porous structure in phosphoric acid. The XRD pattern of PAA shows the amorphous nature of PAA.

Keywords : PAA template, oxalic acid, phosphoric acid.

Introduction

Researchers have a keen interest since a long time to investigate the formation of a highly ordered hexagonal pore array on aluminium. The PAA template has been commercially used as dielectric material in electronic application¹, template for deposition of metals and semiconductors^{2,3}, to fabricate the nanomaterial's like nanowires⁴, nanotubes^{5,6}, nanocones⁷ etc. The PAA also has many interesting catalytic⁸ and optical properties⁹. The PAA template can be used as nano filters with selectivity due to different size pore as used in DNA separation technology¹⁰. Now different types of sensors were developed which are based on nanoporous alumina¹¹. To act as a template for the fabrication of nanomaterials, well characterized regular matrices with porous structure of proper size and shapes are required. Ordered array with large pores were important in the fabrication of useful nanomaterials. The pore opening can be carried by

post treatment in phosphoric acid. The pore size increases with an increase in exposure time to phosphoric acid solution¹². From regular studies it has been found that a well ordered pores were formed in a regime of sulphuric acid at 25 V, oxalic acid at 40 V, and phosphoric acid at 195 V¹³⁻¹⁵. It also has been reported that the self-ordering anodizing of aluminium in phosphoric acid at 195 V produces a pore diameter of about 500 nm¹⁶. So from reported data it has been concluded that the production of regular porous structure in anodization of aluminium in phosphoric acid require high voltages (above 150 V).

The anodization of aluminium in oxalic acid is very stable and produces a very symmetrical regular hexagonal pore array at the low temperature^{17,18}. The anodization process in sulphuric acid and phosphoric acid is not so stable and there is burning due to heat dissipation that causes crack in the film. For anodic oxidation of aluminium in phosphoric acid, a wide range of applied volt-

age has been used in the formation of porous structure (60–190 V), but potentials above 150 V could produce the well-ordered structures¹⁶. Higher constant currents were also applied to get the well order PAA¹⁹. Other than this applied source (high voltage or high current), double anodization for a longer time also improve the microstructure of porous membrane in phosphoric acid²⁰. So there is a need to study more on the morphological and micro structural aspects of aluminium anodization in phosphoric acid.

Fabrication of anodic alumina can be done mainly by two methods : (1) imprintation by master mold/stamp for patterning aluminium and (2) two-step self organised anodization of aluminium. However preparation of master mold from imprintation is time-consuming and expensive process called as lithography²¹. This technique is used in the treatment of small surfaces only but when there is a need of large surface texturing the two-step anodization process produces better ordered arrangement of pores with desired pore diameter and found the best method to fabricate PAA. However these well ordered and hexagonal arrangements of pores requires optimization of anodization conditions. The morphological and microstructural aspects of pores like pore diameter, interpore distance, circularity of pore and pore density depends up on the used electrolyte and anodizing conditions. It has been reported that anodization in sulphuric acid produces fine nanopores with highest pore density²². A pore diameter ranging from 10–300 nm can be obtained by using optimized conditions of electrolyte and applied potential²³. As discussed above, the anodization at higher voltage causes the problem of burning, which leads to higher dissolution with simultaneous growth of anodic oxide film. The anodization at high voltage may also produce more than one pore per cell. This problem can be solved by standardization of conditions of anodization like temperature, concentration or use of some additives in the electrolyte. The first approach used is the lowering in temperature of electrolyte during anodization which reduces the burning. The second approach towards this is to use alcohol as an additive which decreases the temperature of electrolyte significantly and also reduces the joule heating effect on the pore bottoms. The cooling effect on addition of alcohol is due to the evaporation of low freez-

ing alcohols at the aluminium/oxide interface which affect the pore rearrangement time. The effect of ethanol²⁴ and *n*-alcohol (methanol and propanol) has been investigated²⁵. The use of *n*-alcohol in two-step anodization in phosphoric acid at the potential ranging from 110–170 V reduced the complexities of porous structures and sub porous structure of film disappeared.

In this study, we present a way to fabricate symmetric and well ordered porous arrangement in phosphoric acid under low voltage (70 V) than optimum voltage (150–195 V) earlier applied by the researchers for production of best ordered arrangement. This has been done by two-step anodization process and in the first step aluminium samples were anodized in oxalic acid. The influence of time and voltage used in the first step to produce well ordered spherically symmetrical hexagonal porous arrangement in final step anodization in phosphoric acid has been studied.

Experimental

A high-purity aluminium foil (99.997%, Alfa Aesar) was used as starting material. First of all, aluminium substrates were mechanically polished with fine grade Emery paper followed by chemical etching with NaOH (100 g/litre). Then the samples were electro polished in a mixture of HClO₄ : C₂H₅OH (1 : 5) for 3 min at constant voltage of 15 V. After electro polishing the samples were successively rinsed with distilled water, ethanol and dried. The samples were anodized by two-step procedure for the fabrication of alumina film. In the first step, the samples were anodized in 0.3 M oxalic acid for a different extent of time (10, 30, 60, 120 min) and at different voltage (20, 30, 40, 50 V). The prepared alumina layer was washed with an etching mixture of 6 wt% H₃PO₄ and 1.8 wt% H₂Cr₂O₄ at 60 °C for three hours. Then the second anodization was performed for 2 h in 0.3 M phosphoric acid at 70 V. Anodization was performed in a simple electrochemical cell with the magnetic stirrer under the constant temperature of 15 °C. The working surface of sample was 1 cm². A platinum mesh was used as a cathode. The samples were placed at the centre of the platinum mesh.

The surface morphology of the film was investigated by FESEM. The crystallography structure of porous alumina was analysed by high resolution XRD using Rigaku

ultima IV diffractometer in the θ - 2θ configuration and using $\text{CuK}\alpha$ radiation (1.54184 \AA).

Results and discussion

Current time characteristics :

The current-time characteristics plot has been recorded and shown in Figs. 1 and 2 for the 2nd anodization step in $0.3 \text{ M H}_3\text{PO}_4$ at 70 V for pure aluminium. In all samples, the current time curves show local minima within 80 s and the minima was followed by distinct maxima. The minima in the current time plot indicate the growth of compact layer, which has high resistance. The formation of maxima after minima is due to the transformation of compact oxide film in to porous film and then the current density became almost stable due to simultaneous

process of growth and dissolution of the film. The maxima on the curve ascribed to the formation and dissolution of film and occurring of a pore rearrangement process at the surface. The time variation in the first step anodization (in oxalic acid) has little influence on the current time characteristic of the final step proceeded in phosphoric acid (Fig. 2). All current time characteristic plots have same shapes but pore formation start early when the anodization time was 120 min in the first step. Early start of pore formation provides more time for arrangement of pores and produces a better symmetrical porous structure. The current time characteristic as a function of voltage variation in the first step in oxalic acid shows at high current at 40 V (Fig. 1). This also shows the early formation of porous structure.

XRD measurements :

The intact Al_2O_3 , not separated from an aluminium substrate is subjected to XRD. The diffraction pattern shows the amorphous nature of alumina along with peaks corresponding to the aluminium (Fig. 3). The observations are in agreement with Ref.²⁶.

Fig. 1. Current time characteristic of anodization in second step in phosphoric acid as a function of anodization voltage variation in the first step in oxalic acid.

Fig. 2. Current time characteristic of anodization in second step in phosphoric acid as a function of anodization time variation in the first step in oxalic acid.

Fig. 3. XRD pattern of porous anodic alumina.

Reflectance measurements :

Figs. 4 and 5 show the total reflectance spectra of PAA membrane on aluminium. It has been found that reflectance% increases with an increase in wavelength in the range $400\text{--}800 \text{ nm}$ and first step anodization time has no significant influence on reflectance of final porous film in phosphoric acid. However variation in voltage in

Fig. 4. Total reflectance spectra of final PAA intact with aluminium in 0.3 M phosphoric acid at 70 V as a function of anodization in the first step of anodization proceeded in oxalic acid; 10 min (A), 30 min (B), 60 min (C) and 120 min (D).

Fig. 5. Total reflectance spectra of final PAA intact with aluminium in 0.3 M phosphoric acid at 70 V as a function of voltage applied in the first step of anodization proceeded in oxalic acid; 10 V (A), 30 V (B), 40 V (C) and 50 V (D).

first step anodization influences the reflectance spectra to a small extent. The reflectance behaviour of anodized aluminium is originated due to interference behaviour of light between the interfaces of multilayer's²⁷.

Some part of the light is reflected from the top oxide layer, and some of the light part may pass through oxide and then reflected²⁸. After reflection, there is increase or decrease in reflectance that depends on addition of wave which intern depends up on phase difference (destructive and constructive interference). The thickness of PAA was obtained from this reflectance measurement and given in Table 1.

Table 1. Thickness of PAA in second step in phosphoric acid as a function of anodization time and voltage variation in the first step in oxalic acid

Parameters varied in the first step	Thickness
Anodization (V)	(μm)
20	4.11
30	4.13
40	4.32
50	4.09
Time (min)	
10	3.81
30	3.83
60	3.85
120	4.15

The anodization voltage of 40 V and higher anodization time in oxalic acid for better pre texturing, increase the growth rate in second step and slightly thicker PAA membrane is formed in phosphoric acid.

Microstructure and surface morphology :

In the phosphoric acid electrolyte, it is difficult to get the ideal microstructure of highly ordered hexagonal cells. It has been reported that the mechanical stress at metal/oxide interface forces the alumina cells to form regular hexagonal bottom arrays²⁹. In the case of anodization in H_3PO_4 small currents were observed during pore nucleation and formation, which leads to negligible elastic stress and therefore, the field assisted dissolution lead to spatially irregular pore arrays. During the steady-state anodization also the current is low so, the mechanical stress at metal/oxide interface is not enough to regulate the growth of symmetrical pores due to which pore arrays formed in phosphoric acid are irregular³⁰.

It is well known that the anodization in phosphoric acid produces a homogenous porous structure only at voltage above 150 V¹⁶, but in our studies first anodization preceded in oxalic acid leads to a better homogenous regular array of porous structure at voltage of 70 V. Anodization in oxalic acid produces the concave surface after removing the oxide layer in the mixture of 6 wt% H_3PO_4 and 1.8 wt% $\text{H}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_4$ (Fig. 6). These concavities provide better pre texture for the growth of pores during second anodization. The symmetrical pre texture leads to even symmetrical electrical field and there is the formation of ordered porous structure. During the second an-

Fig. 6. Concavities in the film formed after anodization at 40 V preceded in 0.3 M oxalic acid at 20 °C and washed in mixture of 6 wt% H₃PO₄ and 1.8 wt% H₂Cr₂O₄ at 60 °C for 3 h.

odization in H₃PO₄ no more penetration paths were produced due to small currents, and more field was concentrated on the concavity which leads to Al³⁺ field assisted dissolution at bottom of concavities³¹. This event enhances the chances of achieving order pore array despite of weak mechanical forces. It means first anodization impressions guide the growth of pores in 2nd anodization. The application of optimum conditions in the first step in oxalic acid overcomes the pore in pore formation as well as an increase the homogeneity of pores and also removes the limitation of using higher voltages in phosphoric acid anodization for producing better hexagonal porous structure.

A brief qualitative analysis of pores formed in 2nd step can be made in the Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) images as a function of time in the first step anodization. FFT images show the presence of bright points in the corners of the hexagon (Fig. 7c). From FFT images, it is confirmed that there is hexagonal arrangement with spherical pores. Further increase in anodization time in first step gives FFT images with more distinct bright points at the corner of hexagon confirming the best hexagonal nanoporous arrangement. Applied potential also shows an appreciable effect on nanoporous arrangement. FFT based analysis shows that the best arrangement is for applied voltage of 40 V, where the dots are brightest in the form of a hexagon (Fig. 8). At lower and higher potential than 40 V, FFT image shows a ring, and not much distinct bright was observed confirming less order structure of nano pores. There are various information's provided by the FFT images of FE-SEM³² like pore arrangement, uniformity of pores and interpore distances. In the uniform

Fig. 7. FE-SEM images of aluminium after final anodization in 0.3 M phosphoric acid at 70 V as a function of time applied in the first step of anodization preceded in oxalic acid; 10 min (A), 30 min (B), 60 min (C) and 120 min (D).

porous arrangement, the FFT images show very distinct bright points in the form of a hexagon while just a ring was observed in unsymmetrical porous pattern.

From the FE-SEM images (Fig. 8) it is clearly observed that with increase in applied voltage of anodization in the first step, the homogeneity of pore increases in second step anodization in phosphoric acid, but this happened only up to a voltage of 40 V. If there is a further

Fig. 8. FE-SEM images of aluminium after final anodization in 0.3 M phosphoric acid at 70 V as a function of voltage applied in the first step of anodization preceded in oxalic acid; 10 V (A), 30 V (B), 40 V (C) and 50 V (D).

increase in voltage from 40 to 50 V, then there is disturbance in homogeneity of pores in the finally formed PAA in phosphoric acid. Lowering the potential to the 30 V and 20 V results with irregular pore with a different pore diameter. It predicts that applied voltage in the first step has a significant influence on the final pore formation in the second step. It means that the applied voltage of 40 V in the first step creates the best pre-texture to grow the pores in second step in a well-ordered manner. Figs. 9 and 10 presents the variation of pore density as a function

Fig. 9. Pore density (no. of pores per unit area) in final PAA in 0.3 M phosphoric acid at 70 V as a function of time applied in the first step of anodization proceeded in oxalic acid; 10 min. (A), 30 min (B), 60 min (C) and 120 min (D).

Fig. 10. Pore density (no. of pores per unit area) in final PAA in 0.3 M phosphoric acid at 70 V as a function of voltage applied in the first step of anodization proceeded in oxalic acid; 10 V (A), 30 V (B), 40 V (C) and 50 V (D).

of anodization time and applied voltage in the first step in oxalic acid. The lesser interpore distance at 40 V leads to higher pore density. The voltage lower and higher than 40 V produces higher pore diameter 155–170 nm but these pores were not symmetrical. So it is clear that by controlling the anodization parameters in first step, we can control the pore diameter of finally formed PAA. It has been found that there is no significance difference at anodization of 20 V and 30 V. The regularity of the pores was also disturbed when anodization voltage was 50 V, which produces non uniform concavity in the first step leads to less ordered porous anodic alumina in H_3PO_4 .

Duration of first step anodization has also an impact on the pore diameter. Anodization for longer time increases the thickness of film and causes deeper pre-texturing at the aluminium surface so that after removal of oxide layer ordered concavity remains at the aluminium surface. The concavity serves as nucleation sites for pore growth. Fig. 7 shows the variation in the pore microstructure of finally formed PAA as a function of anodization time in the first step conducted in oxalic acid. From FESEM images, it has been observed that with an increase in time of anodization in first step the uniformity of pores increases. It has been observed that up to anodization of two hours, there is formation of pores with different diameter ranging from 90–120 nm. Thus anodization for a longer time leads to a better pre-texture in the form of concavities for the growth of pores during second anodization in a well ordered manner with symmetrical pores. The less ordered pre-texture by the first step anodization causes slow and non uniform growth of oxide film in the final step, which leads to dissolution of pore wall due to long exposure of porous alumina to phosphoric acid. The dissolution of pore wall causes pore in pore arrangement (Fig. 7a,b and Fig. 8d). The most symmetrical pores were produced when the time of anodization was 120 min at a voltage of 40 V in the first step. At these optimized conditions, the interpore distance and pore diameter was found 115 ± 6 nm and 97 ± 13 nm respectively.

Conclusions

From the studies, we conclude that parameters used in the first step anodization highly influence the origin of pores in the second step of anodization. Anodizations of

aluminium in oxalic acid in first step provide a better pre-tecture for the production of symmetrical pores in final step. It was observed that the longer the first step of anodization in oxalic acid best is the porous structure produced in the final step anodization in phosphoric acid. The anodization for longer time in the first step creates better pre-tuxturing and it will leads to the production of highly ordered PAA. The best voltage in the first step in oxalic acid anodization was found to be 40 V. Thus in total, we conclude that the aluminium first anodized in oxalic acid at 40 V for more than 60 min leads to the formation of symmetrical porous structures in second step at low voltage in H₃PO₄.

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